

An open research data evaluation model for translational research projects

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Keywords

[Open Data, Open Research Data, Translational Research, Evaluation Model]

STRUCTURED ABSTRACT

Aim of your contribution

The main objective of our contribution to the conference is to reveal some information science issues related with drivers and inhibitors to share and use open research data and the practical requirements for it in translational research projects, as well as the question about if triple helix initiatives engaging academia, industry and government in Colombia are ready to implement the change towards an open research data world. This research is an untold story because the case study we explored does not have similar background in the bioeconomy area and literature regarding these issues are scarce.

Value of your contribution

The value of our contribution is to discover what an information science professional could analyze and develop when working in international, interorganizational and interdisciplinary research projects under the triple helix model, in which sharing data is challenging and overly complex. Participants of the event will learn how to identify requirements for open research data initiatives in research projects from a methodological and practical view, and how to translate them in an open research data evaluation model that can guide researchers when implementing open data solutions. From a social view, implications relate to direct benefits of open data, such as access to data, visibility of research, reproducibility and repeatability analysis, transparency, and others.

Research outline

GAT is a scientific program led by the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana, whose purpose is the generation of therapeutic alternatives in cancer from Colombian native plants through translational research and development processes, articulated in environmentally and economically sustainable value systems (Fiorentino, 2022). The research ecosystem is a case

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of how a combination of Triple Helix collaboration (Lee et al., 2015) between Universities, Pharmaceutical companies and Government contributes to creating knowledge and value about bioeconomy in health. The GAT program is enacted through a multidisciplinary network of 125 researchers from 20 different institutions and 7 countries, working on areas such as oncology, immunobiology, chemical, pharmacology, neurology, engineering, among others.

Discovering new drugs in GAT involve analysis and experimentation in 10 interrelated research projects producing data, information, and knowledge every day, evidenced in hundreds of datasets, reports, papers, posters, notes, laboratory notebooks, patents, professional secrets, among other information resources. In this sense, for GAT researchers and institutions it is important and useful to know about open science practices and guidelines that they must follow to facilitate the current research activities (Sullivan et al., 2021), but also to create new networks and alliances from the use and reuse of scientific data, feeding new research initiatives, and exchanging scientific information with other ecosystems.

However, several issues were identified in this research regarding the appropriation and implementation of Open Science in GAT (Robles, 2022). First, GAT lacks an open research data policy guiding practices for the management of data and information. Therefore, the whole scientific information stored in computational platforms and information systems remains private and for the exclusive use of GAT researchers. Second, GAT does not have a data and information management framework and so different management criteria are adopted by researchers in every project. Third, knowledge about open science practices and open research data in translational research are scarce. And four, researchers still consider that open data may not benefit them even though conventional drug development models are widely perceived as opaque and inefficient (Shaw, 2017).

Grounded on a design science research approach (Hevner et al., 2004), this project is based on three main iterations: the exploration of the open research data knowledge base; the identification of the technical requirements of GAT in terms of open research data; and the design of an open data management model for the ecosystem jointly with the evaluation. The design product (evaluation model for translational research projects) is based on open data planning, monitoring, and evaluation processes, and it develops over identification and implementation of open data management elements, which are naturally applicable to GAT. The model is operationalized through a set of evaluation criteria for each open data factor (accessibility, portability, confidentiality, availability, quality, among others). The model was assessed through questionnaires and debriefings sessions with data scientists and PI's of GAT.

In this research, we concluded that the GAT program should strengthen the planning processes of research projects under the open science umbrella (Méndez, 2017), through

documentation and guidelines for open research data management. Literacy about open research data and, in more general terms, open science, is imperative for the scientific ecosystem to promote a data-sharing culture inside GAT but also, permeating the institutional actor participating on it. As a main limitation of this research, we found evidence that there is a gap in literature about the interlink between translational research and open science. Consequently, authors expanded the theoretical scope of the literature review involving studies about medicine, pharmacology, and genetics. Further research may be useful in this topic, but also, in developing a quantitative indicator for each factor composing the open research data model proposed.

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Suggested Citation

[Robles, D. & Nova, N] (2022). [An open research data evaluation model for translational research projects]. Trends in Information Science – The ASIS&ST European Chapter Research Series. 09-11 June 2021. Virtual conference.